

Household district	Study Number	Household Identification Number

CONSENT FORM

STUDY TITLE

3. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

Informed Consent Form for Parents/Guardians of Project Participants

Please circle Yes or No to confirm whether you agree or do not agree with each of the points below:

I agree that my child.....(full name of child/person) for whom I am a guardian may take part in the above Malawi-Liverpool Wellcome Trust research project.	Yes / No
The project has been explained to and to me, and we have read the Participant Information Sheet, which I may keep for my records.	Yes / No
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I and my child have had the chance to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers that we have been given. 	Yes / No
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that agreeing to take part means that I am willing to allow my child to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> be interviewed by the researcher, who will take notes during the interview, provide one sample of faeces for the research study at three time points (Time point 1, Time point 2= 1 month after Time point 1, Time point 3= 6 months following Time point 1) 	Yes / No
I agree that should <i>E. coli</i> or non-typhoidal <i>Salmonella</i> be found the sample provided by my child that the bacteria or bacterial DNA will be shipped to the UK	Yes / No

or Kenya to undergo whole genome sequencing. No human sample will leave Malawi	
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- **Data Protection**

The information obtained during the interview will be held and processed by the researchers to be used as part of the analysis for this research project

- I understand that any information (full name of child/person) provides is confidential, and that no information that could lead to the identification of any individual will be disclosed in any reports on the project, or to any other party. No identifiable personal data will be published. The identifiable data will not be shared with any other organisation.
- I also understand that’s (full name of child/person) participation is voluntary, that s/he can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that s/he or I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way.

Participant’s Name: (please print)

Participant’s Age:.....

Parent’s/Guardian’s Name

Your relationship to participant:

Signature/thumbprint of Parent/Guardian:

.....Date:.....

Confirmation of Impartial Witness:

I, _____, confirm that _____ has agreed to take part in the above research study

Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome
Clinical Research Programme

THE COLLEGE OF MEDICINE
Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome Trust
Clinical Research Programme

www.mlw.medcol.mw

Signature of staff collecting the consent: _____ (Date) _____

Chichewa speaking contact:

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